

Importance of Goat Milk for Human Health

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Introduction

Milk

The white liquid meal known as milk is generated by mammals' mammary glands. For young mammals, including breastfed human infants, it serves as their main source of nutrition until they are able to process solid food. Milk immunity is influenced by immune factors and immune-modulating substances. Colostrum, or early-lactation milk, is a type of milk that has antibodies in it that boost immunity and lower overall illness risk. In addition to lactose and saturated fat, milk contains a variety of minerals, such as calcium and protein. Dairy milk is a crop that is obtained from farm animals.

Goat milk

The most popular dairy product worldwide is goat milk. Its percentage of dairy consumers worldwide is almost 65-72% due to its high consumption level. It's also because maintaining goats is simpler than maintaining cows. The statement is particularly true for developing nations when the populace faces resource scarcity. Goat milk also contains healthy lipids, proteins, and calories. Consequently, goat milk is preferred by most people over cow milk. Goat milk is one of the greatest substitutes for cow's milk if you're looking for one. One of the healthiest nutraceutical beverages is goat milk, which is high in oligosaccharides, which are derived from lactose. It

is frequently used to make various kinds of yoghurt and cheese. Goat farming is a vital source of income in a number of nations, primarily in the Middle East and Mediterranean regions. Goats are revered as the "Cow of the Poor Man." Several studies have shown that goat milk protein have anti-inflammatory effects, which may benefit people suffering from chronic inflammatory conditions such as arthritis, asthma, and allergies. Goats milk contains several types of proteins, including casiens, whey protein, and immunoglobulins. While cow milk is slightly acidic, goat milk is alkaline. Alkaline diets have been linked with better cardiovascular and neurological health. Goat milk also contains monounsaturated fats, which can decrease risk of heart disease and type 2 diabetes. Goat milk is thicker and creamier than cow milk or plant milks, and goat milk has more nutrients that may offer health benefits. For example:

- Easier to digest
- Less risk of milk allergies
- Better heart health

Goat milk

A cup of goat milk has

Calories -170, Protein -9grams, Fat -10 grams, Carbohydrates 11 grams, sugar -11grams, cholesterol-25 miligrams

Nutritional information –The differences in the nutritional information of goat milk and cow milk

Nutritional value of goat milk

Goat milk contains the following nutrient in it.

Nutrient	Amount per 100 g	Nutrient	Amount per 100 g
Protein	3.56 g	Calcium	134 mg
Fats	4.14 g	Potassium	204 mg
Carbohydrates	4.45 g	Magnesium	14 mg
Water	87 g	Phosphorus	111 mg
Energy	69 kcal	Sodium	50 mg
Sugar	4.45 g	Copper	0.046 mg
Iron	0.05 mg	Zinc	0.3 mg
Manganese	0.018 mg	Vitamin B5	0.31 mg
Selenium	1.4 µg	Vitamin B6	0.046 mg
Vitamin A	57 µg	Vitamin B9	1 µg
Vitamin B1	0.048 mg	Vitamin B12	0.07 µg
Vitamin B2	0.138 mg	Vitamin C	1.3 mg
Vitamin B3	0.277 mg	Vitamin D	51 IU
Vitamin E	0.07 mg		

Table 1 Nutrient present in 100g of goat milk

Properties of Goat milk

- It may act as antioxidant
- It might act as anti-inflammatory
- It may act as anti-mucosal
- It might act as anti-cancer
- It may boost the immunity
- It may act as anti-microbial
- It might act as prebiotics
- It may boost the immunity

Benefits of Goat Milk

Here are the 10 health benefits of goat milk

1. Good for Skin

Studies have shown that milk is an effective element for treating skin issues. For instance, it lessens blackheads and acne. It also aids in skin smoothing, whitening, and moisturization. Beyond the normal benefits of milk on the skin, goat milk has additional benefits for your skin.

The pH of human skin is the same as that of goat milk. This indicates that using goat milk to cleanse your face won't damage the acid mantle or the skin's natural flora. Goat milk will therefore be quite beneficial if you have sensitive skin conditions like psoriasis or eczema. Lactic acid and fatty acids included in goat milk help to restore the skin's protective layer. According to studies, goat milk's low content of alpha hydroxy acids (AHA) helps moisturize, gently exfoliate, and heal skin damaged by the sun. It also helps to produce skin that is notably softer. Additionally, probiotics are included to promote the development of healthy skin bacteria.

2. Promotes a Healthy Weight Gain

Diabetes, high blood pressure, heart disease, and stroke are all reduced by maintaining a healthy weight. In addition, it lowers the risk of developing cancer. Goat milk has higher calories per serving than other forms of milk. Its nutritional profile is comparable to that of cow's milk, though. Consequently, a healthy weight increase results from the additional calories.

According to a study, undernourished children may benefit from using goat milk instead of cow's milk for rehabilitation. Therefore, you should drink goat milk if you are underweight and want to gain weight in a healthy way.

3. Goat Milk is Easier to Digest

Goat milk has 20% fewer fat globules than cow's milk. These are therefore simpler to understand. For those who are lactose intolerant, it is a great substitute for cow's milk because of its decreased lactose content.

Goat milk facilitates easy digestion and a smooth metabolism, according to research. To investigate its effects on hunger and protein metabolism, more research is necessary.

4. Increases Platelet Count

Selenium insufficiency and a decrease in blood platelet count are two serious consequences of dengue illness. Goat milk, however, may aid in the treatment of dengue patients by boosting blood platelets, according to studies. This is so because its

primary ingredient is selenium. Furthermore, it facilitates the body's digestion and utilization of different minerals through metabolism.

5. Goat Milk Helps Prevent Milk Allergies in Kids

There is a fair percentage of A2 casein in goat milk. For instance, there are roughly 3.6 grams of A2 casein in 100 milliliters of goat milk. A2 casein, like human breast milk, has a high protein content. Consequently, it guards against inflammatory illnesses including colitis and IBS. Goat milk is typically given to infants as their first protein source following breastfeeding. They are therefore less likely than cow's milk to cause milk allergies.

6. Goat Milk Prevents Arteriosclerosis

The disease known as arteriosclerosis causes the arteries that supply the body and heart with oxygen and nutrients to thicken and stiffen. It thereby limits the amount of blood that reaches your tissues and organs. A tiny amount of xanthine oxidase, an enzyme needed to create uric acid, has been found in goat milk. When xanthine oxidase enters the circulation, it may result in cardiac problems. Thus, a lower concentration of this enzyme is necessary to reduce the incidence of arteriosclerosis.

7. Prevents Insulin Resistance

Having enough insulin in your body aids in blood glucose regulation. When your bloodstream has too much glucose, it also replenishes the remaining glucose in your liver. Goat milk has been shown to prevent insulin resistance. Blood sugar levels rise in the body as a result of insulin resistance. Consequently, type 2 diabetes may eventually emerge from it. It is more troublesome because there are usually no signs.

8. Helps Reduce Cholesterol Levels

A study found that goat milk might raise the amount of cholesterol secreted by the biliary system. Furthermore, it results in a drop in the concentration of plasma cholesterol. Consuming goat milk also lowers the level of plasma triglycerides. Consequently, it has a favorable

impact on lipid metabolism, much like olive oil (normal diet). Cells synthesise and break down lipids through lipid metabolism. It also plays a role in the synthesis of cell membranes. Goat milk is good for those with health issues such as elevated blood cholesterol. It might aid in lowering cholesterol levels in the gallbladder and arteries.

9. Prevents Anaemia

Rich in calcium, iron, magnesium, and phosphorus is goat milk. These minerals are easily absorbed and digested by our systems. Goat milk therefore aids in the treatment of nutritional deficits including bone demineralization. It also corrects deficiencies in magnesium and iron. It improves the body's absorption of iron even more. Additionally, RBC production is enhanced by goat milk. For this reason, people with osteoporosis, anemia, or problems with malabsorption should drink goat milk.

10. Naturally Homogenized

If cow milk is allowed to settle, it begins to separate. However, goat milk does not experience this. The homogenization process is to blame. The process of forcing fat globules in milk to break apart is known as homogenization. Emulsification—the blending of fat and water—is the goal. Processing goat milk does not require it. It is therefore the healthiest choice that is easily accessible to us.

11. Help in Environmental Protection

Cows' digestive systems often result in excessive flatulence. It escapes as methane, a greenhouse gas that destroys the ozone layer and the environment greatly. Thus, cows that are raised for milk indirectly contribute significantly to both global warming and ozone depletion processes. Therefore, the production of goat milk shields humans from the negative consequences of climate change. Thus, it is the ideal moment to practice environmental responsibility.

Best Ways to Use Goat Milk

Some intriguing uses for goat milk are listed below.

- In every dish, goat milk makes a great substitute for milk products.
- It can be added to smoothies and shakes. It also tastes great added to any kind of latte.
- It tastes great in creamy soups, rich sauces, and overnight oats.
- Goat milk is an easy substitute for milk on the digestive system when baking.
- Goat milk butter can be used to make pastries and frostings.
- Goat milk is a great ingredient to use while making ice cream.

Conclusion

The milk from goats is rich in nutrients. It is even more nutritious than cow's milk. Thus, it also aids in our absorption of some nutrients. For protein, calcium, and lipids, it is a more wholesome and organic choice. These are the causes of its highest consumption in the globe. You may simply incorporate goat milk into your daily diet by taking the necessary precautions and being mindful of any potential adverse effects. Recall that 200 ml, or three servings, of goat milk meets each person's calcium needs. Enjoy the benefits of the changes it will bring about for you.

References:

- Lad S, Aparnathi K, Mehta B, Velpula S. Goat Milk in Human Nutrition and Health – A Review. *International Journal of Current Microbiology and Applied Sciences* [Internet]. 2017;6(5):1781-1792. Available from: https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Bhavbhuti-Mehta/publication/317021326_Goat_Milk_in_Human_Nutrition_and_Health_-_A_Review/links/5931404345851553b68c588f/Goat-Milk-in-Human-Nutrition-and-Health-A-Review.pdf
- Milk, goat, fluid, with added vitamin D [Internet]. FoodData Central. 2022. Available from: <https://fdc.nal.usda.gov/fdc-app.html#/food-details/171278/nutrients>
- Yadav A, Singh J, Yadav S. Composition, nutritional and therapeutic values of goat milk: A review. *Asian Journal of Dairy and Food Research* [Internet].

2016;35(2). Available from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/303721433_Composition_nutritional_and_therapeutic_values_of_goat_milk_A_review

Hamam A, Salman S, Elfaruk M, Alsaleem K. Goat Milk: Compositional, Technological, Nutritional, and Therapeutic Aspects. [Internet]. 2021; Available from: <https://www.preprints.org/manuscript/202108.0097/v1>

Milk – Better Health Channel [Internet]. Betterhealth.vic.gov.au. 2022. Available from: <https://www.betterhealth.vic.gov.au/health/healthyliving/milk>

Unpasteurized Milk Can Pose a Serious Health Risk [Internet]. U.S. Food and Drug Administration. 2022. Available from: <https://www.fda.gov/food/buy-store-serve-safe-food/dangers-raw-milk-unpasteurized-milk-can-pose-serious-health-risk>

Nutritional and Health Aspects of Goat Milk Consumption [Internet]. Dergipark.org.tr. 2015. Available from: <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/download/article-file/1186419>